

GENERAL PRINCIPLES OF ORAL LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: *This article gives information about some stages of oral language and how to improve this skill among children. As well as, provides useful advice for people who are going to develop their oral language abilities.*

Key: *words: broader literacy, sophisticated users of language, note-taking skills, cognitive processing, recall mechanism.*

Why oral language development matters

The link between oral language and broader literacy development is well established. Reading proficiency is built on a wide knowledge and fluent use of oral language and teacher can do much to support students in this across all content areas and with all year levels.

Building oral language across all the year levels

Oral language skills continue to be important throughout all the school years, in fact, throughout life. Thus oral language development is not just the domain of the early childhood teacher; teacher can continue to help students become more articulate and sophisticated users of language throughout their school years and this equip them for fuller and more rewarding participation in life.

Allowing wait time

Waiting at least 3-5 seconds for children to respond is difficult but important. In reality this should be called 'thinking time' rather than wait time, because some children need additional time to process information before composing their answer. Answer tend to be more complex if students are given more time to formulate their answer. The acronym OWL (observe, wait, listen) has been successfully used to help remember the importance of giving children time to respond.

Referring children for assessment of significant speech and language delays

Referred to a speech pathologist via the school reporting system is recommended if a child's speech or language is significantly delayed or different from peers, particularly in the early years of school. Investigate also whether a hearing assessment has been conducted.

Teaching active listening

Listening is a core component of oral language. Some students can hear, but are not active listeners. Active listening requires selective and sustained attention, working memory, cognitive processing and information storage and recall mechanism. Teachers can help students develop these skills by giving them tasks, such as listening for specific or key information; listening to answer specific questions and listening to follow instructions. Barrier games and story grammar activities require active listening and help to improve oral language as well. For older students, teaching note-taking skills from oral input also develops listening skills.

Exploring story books together

Reading stories (narrative texts) provides the perfect oral language support, providing both stimulation and motivation. Sharing a book encompasses much more than simply reading it. Picture books can also stimulate language promote a rich discussion of ideas. Older children can benefit from having books read to them-even those who can read for themselves. Teachers can read books that expose the students to more sophisticated vocabulary and syntactic structures than students would be able to read alone, and that promote discussion about diverse and important topics that may not otherwise be raised.

Providing opportunities for social interaction

Oral language develops through practice, but most talking in classrooms is done by the teacher. Scientists found that 73% of preschool children's time in the United States was spent without any direct teacher-child interaction. Those interactions that did take place took the form of closed questions that did not build oral language facility or literacy skills. Only 8% of children's time was spent in elaborated interactions with teachers. Considering the increased size and complexity of older year levels, we can assume that generally the percentages are no better for older children and are probably worse.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES:

1. [http://academia.com/article/oral language](http://academia.com/article/oral%20language)

